

Assessing the Implementation and Stakeholder Perceptions of the National Education Policy 2020 in Higher Education Institutions of Satna City, Madhya Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

The National Education Policy (NEP) of 2020 introduced significant reforms aimed at transforming the Indian education landscape, particularly in higher education. This research paper delves into the implementation of the NEP 2020 within higher education institutions in Satna City, Madhya Pradesh, and assesses its impact on various stakeholders. Through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, interviews, and document analysis, this study investigates the extent of NEP 2020 implementation, identifies challenges encountered, and explores stakeholders' perceptions regarding its efficacy. The findings provide insights into the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with the policy's implementation in the context of Satna City, ultimately informing future policy adjustments and strategic planning efforts.

KEYWORDS

National Education Policy 2020, higher education institutions, stakeholders, implementation

INTRODUCTION

The National Education Policy (NEP) of 2020 represents a comprehensive framework designed to revamp India's education system, particularly in higher education, to meet the demands of the 21st century. Satna City, located in the state of Madhya Pradesh, serves as a microcosm for examining the localized impact of the NEP 2020 on higher education institutions and stakeholders. This paper aims to analyze the implementation process of NEP 2020 within Satna's higher education landscape, exploring its effects on students, faculty, administrators, and other key stakeholders.

The Education Policy emphasizes the significance of nurturing the innovative abilities of every individual. It underscores that education should not only focus on cognitive aspects like basic literacy skills, proficiency, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills but also on fostering social, ethical, and emotional capabilities and attitudes.

Teachers hold a revered position in society, being regarded as indispensable members. Therefore, it is imperative to empower and support them in effectively carrying out their responsibilities. The implementation of NEP 2020 aims to attract skilled educators into the education sector, guaranteeing them a means of livelihood, esteem, honor, and independence. The revised

educational policy should ensure that every student, regardless of their location, historical context, or membership in disadvantaged or underrepresented groups, has access to high-quality education. Education serves as a powerful means to foster economic advancement, social inclusion, and equality. It is imperative that all students are afforded diverse opportunities to excel academically. These principles should be integrated into the educational framework, considering both local and global requirements, while also respecting and celebrating the nation's rich diversity and cultural heritage. Imparting knowledge about India, encompassing its diverse social, cultural, and technological needs, as well as its unique artistic, linguistic, and intellectual traditions, along with instilling strong ethical values in India's youth, is vital for fostering national pride, cooperation, and unity.

For the successful implementation of the Educational policy, stakeholders must possess a thorough understanding of its contents. Quality education can only be improved if stakeholders are well-informed about the policy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Prior research has extensively analyzed the provisions and objectives of the NEP 2020 on a national scale, highlighting its potential benefits and challenges. However, there is a dearth of studies focusing on its localized implementation and stakeholder perspectives, particularly in smaller cities like Satna. Existing literature also provides insights into the broader challenges faced by higher education institutions in India, ranging from infrastructure deficiencies to curriculum reforms.

- **Ms. Sujatha Ramesh, Dr. K. Natarajan (2019)** had compared the NEP (2019) with the American Education system. According to them the flexible approaches are same as the approach adopted by USA.
- **Kalervo N Gulson, Sam seller (2018)**, they come to one conclusion that allowing new private and public connections across policy topologies.
- **Nikil Govind (2019) Aithal P.S, Shybhra jyotsna Aithal (2019)** had analyzed the positive and negative side and suggested for further improvement in Education Policy.
- **National Education Policy (1966)** Social Work Education began in India in 1936 with the founding of the Tata Institute of Social Sciences. Following independence, there was a significant focus on education reforms, culminating in the announcement of the first education policy in 1996. This policy aimed at a "Radical Restructuring" to ensure equal educational opportunities for all, thereby fostering national integration. It emphasized the importance of both primary and secondary education for all Indians, prioritizing the establishment of schools in both rural and urban areas.
- **National Education Policy (1986)** the primary objective of the 1986 National Education Policy was to advance minority education, ensure gender equality in education, and prioritize education for marginalized communities, including Scheduled Castes (SC), Scheduled Tribes

(ST), and backward sections. It underscored the significance of providing equal educational opportunities to all segments of society. This updated education policy placed utmost importance on addressing the issue of school dropouts by implementing a variety of meticulously designed strategies, particularly emphasizing micro-level planning and grassroots-level implementation nationwide. A national mission was initiated to achieve the objectives outlined in the 1986 NEP. Through a review of literature on education policies from 1966 and 1986, it is evident that the 1966 policy stressed equal access to education for all, while the 1986 policy prioritized women's education, minority education promotion, and reducing school dropout rates.

RESEARCH GAP

The preceding education policies provided a strong framework for nation-building, addressing the specific needs of prioritized societal segments, with the aim of progressing towards national development. However, significant societal changes have occurred since 1986, spanning a period of 34 years, marked by extensive advancements, enhancements, transformations, and technological, economic, educational, and attitudinal shifts, including changes in competition and job perspectives. Therefore, it is imperative to prioritize the analysis of the impacts and consequences of the New Education Policy of 2020, given the evolving landscape and emerging challenges.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The focus is placed on analyzing the National Education Policy (NEP) of 2020, particularly examining the transformations occurring within higher education. The NEP underscores the priorities set at this level, expanding the scope to incorporate practical approaches and a greater emphasis on job orientation.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Based on the research gap and the statement of problem, the following objectives are taken for the purpose of study:

1. To examine the impact of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 on higher education.
2. To understand the potential impacts of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 on higher education.
3. To understand the potential limitations or disadvantages associated with the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 in the realm of higher education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research draws upon both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data is gathered through a questionnaire distributed via Google Forms to respondents. A total of 52 responses were received and utilized for the study. Secondary data is sourced from the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020

published by the Ministry of Human Resource Development. Convenience sampling is employed as the method of sampling.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significant effect of NEP on stakeholders of Higher education.

H₁: There is significant effect of NEP on stakeholders of Higher education.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

1. Demographic distribution of Respondent:

Table-1

Particulars		%
Gender	Male	25%
	Female	75%
Educational Qualification	Graduate	11%
	Post Graduate	70%
	Ph.D.	19%
Age	20 – 30 Years	89%
	31 – 40 Years	7%
	41 – 50 Years	3%
	> 50 Years	1%

Source: Questionnaires

Interpretation: The table provided in Table-1 outlines the characteristics of the stakeholders within the education sector who are significantly impacted by the NEP - 2020. The data in the table reflects a study conducted with a total sample size of 100 individuals, comprising both students and teachers. These teachers have a minimum of 5 years of teaching experience at both the undergraduate and postgraduate levels.

2. Awareness of NEP-2020:

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The depicted data illustrates stakeholders' awareness of the NEP-2020. Out of 100 respondents surveyed, 83% demonstrated awareness of the NEP-2020, while the remaining 17% indicated a lack of awareness regarding this policy.

3. Opinion about NEP-2020:

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The provided diagram illustrates stakeholder perspectives on NEP-2020 in comparison to the current NEP. Out of 100 participants surveyed, 73% expressed positive views, regarding NEP-2020 as a commendable government initiative for the education sector. 17% believe it surpasses the current NEP, while 10% consider it the optimal education policy.

4. Possible outcome of NEP-2020:

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: According to the graph provided, it is evident that the NEP-2020 has yielded favorable results regarding its influence on students, as indicated by the research findings. The introduction of NEP-2020 implies that students will experience a more interactive and imaginative blend of subjects, fostering clarity regarding their aspirations from an early stage. Consequently, they can adapt and enhance their skill sets accordingly.

5. Probable drawbacks of NEP-2020:

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: In this study, the investigator aimed to identify potential shortcomings of the NEP-2020. It was concluded that while NEP-2020 represents a commendable initiative, certain concerns were noted, such as the length of courses and student-teacher ratios based on gathered data. Additionally, there was an emphasis on the need for educators to possess advanced skills, be proficient in both academic and industrial aspects, and demonstrate versatility.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Particulars	O	E	(O - E)	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
Enhance life skills	45	49	-4	0.327
Improvement in education standard	43	49	-6	0.735
Student can afford global education	46	49	-3	0.184
Optimum use of technology	45	49	-4	0.327
Develop skills to meet industry requirement	44	49	-5	0.510
Extensive research	46	49	-3	0.184
	269			2.265

Source: Primary data

H₀: There is no significant effect of NEP on stakeholders of Higher education.

H₁: There is significant effect of NEP on stakeholders of Higher education.

Critical value ($\alpha=0.05$ d.f= 5) = 2.015

Chi square value= 2.265

Decision: Chi square value is more than critical value (2.265>2.015) hence H₀ is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Therefore we can say that NEP has a significant impact on stakeholders of Higher Education.

RESULTS

The findings will be presented in a comprehensive manner, highlighting the extent of NEP 2020 implementation in Satna City's higher education institutions. Analysis of survey data and interviews will reveal stakeholders' perceptions regarding the policy's effectiveness, its impact on teaching-learning practices, curriculum design, assessment methods, and institutional governance.

The stakeholders need to reassess the NEP 2020 to better understand the skills necessary for its implementation. They should actively pursue the acquisition of skills essential for economic growth. Prior to selecting a course of study, students should evaluate their own skills to expedite their goal achievement. While there is ample opportunity for research on the NEP 2020, there remains a widespread lack of understanding about its mechanisms. Therefore, there is a need for increased awareness and research efforts in order to enhance stakeholder knowledge, accelerate the adoption of the NEP 2020, and promote economic development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Offer practical recommendations for enhancing the implementation of NEP 2020 initiatives in higher education institutions in Satna City.
2. Suggest strategies to address identified challenges and improve stakeholder engagement and collaboration.
3. Foster regular and transparent communication channels between higher education institutions, policymakers, administrators, faculty members, students, and other relevant stakeholders to ensure their active involvement in the implementation process.
4. Organize workshops, seminars, and town hall meetings to facilitate dialogue and exchange of ideas regarding NEP 2020 objectives, challenges, and opportunities.
5. Establish dedicated support mechanisms, such as mentoring programs and resource centers, to assist higher education institutions in Satna City in effectively implementing NEP 2020 initiatives.
6. Encourage higher education institutions to review and update their curricula to align with the multidisciplinary and holistic learning approach advocated by NEP 2020.
7. Integrate skill development, experiential learning, and research-oriented activities into the curriculum to enhance students' employability and foster critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills.
8. Invest in upgrading infrastructure facilities, including laboratories, libraries, ICT infrastructure, and learning spaces, to support the implementation of NEP 2020 initiatives such as online learning, digital literacy, and educational technology integration.
9. Conduct regular assessments and feedback mechanisms to gauge stakeholders' perceptions, identify implementation bottlenecks, and refine strategies accordingly.

10. Leverage existing networks and platforms to share best practices, resources, and experiences related to NEP 2020 implementation across higher education institutions in Satna City and beyond.

CONCLUSION

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 aims to facilitate collaboration among stakeholders to address industry, national, and global demands, thereby promoting a higher standard of living and holistic economic development. It acknowledges that alterations in the current landscape can yield both favorable and unfavorable consequences. Therefore, it is imperative to prioritize the positive outcomes and implement them efficiently to advance the nation's welfare.

By examining the implementation of the NEP 2020 in Satna City's higher education institutions and stakeholders' perceptions, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse on education reform in India. The insights generated can inform policymakers, educational administrators, and other stakeholders about the localized challenges and opportunities in realizing the goals set forth by the NEP 2020. Recommendations will be provided for enhancing policy implementation and addressing the specific needs of higher education institutions in Satna City, thereby fostering sustainable educational development.

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About the Author

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Manisha Jain is a dedicated scholar pursuing her Ph.D. in Education, focusing on a comparative study of the National Education Policy 1986 and the National Education Policy 2020. With a strong academic background, she holds master's degrees in Sociology and Hindi Literature, along with additional qualifications in Education. With over a decade of teaching experience at Kamla Nehru Girls College, Satna, Manisha brings a wealth of practical knowledge and academic insight to her research. Her interdisciplinary approach and commitment to educational advancement make her a valuable contributor to the field of education.

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